

ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK IDIOMS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the unique aspects of idioms in English and Uzbek and the important points about idioms. An idiom is a phrase whose meaning does not come from the sum of the meanings of the words in it. Idiomatic expressions are mainly used in everyday communication. Such phrases are quickly memorized and functionally equivalent. They also serve to express feelings beautifully.

Introduction. An idiom is a widely used saying or expression containing a figurative meaning that differs from the phrase's literal meaning. The word "idiom" comes from the Greek word "idioma," meaning peculiar phrasing. A unit of speech or phrase that is unique to a particular language and cannot be exactly translated into other languages. When translating phrases into another language, it is necessary to find their equivalent in that language. Idioms are one of the most complex areas of language learning, especially in English, and require a special approach. Usually, people translate idiomatic expressions directly, and this sometimes leads to funny translations.

For example, the idiom "**Ochiq yuz**" in **Uzbek** is not literally translated as "*Open face*" when translated into English. Maybe in one word, it means *sincere*.

Discussion. Or when the **English** phrase "**able to fig a mirror**" is translated into Uzbek, there is no direct translation. That is, it may not mean "*oynada tura olmoq*", but it means "*bardosh bermoq, oyoqda turmoq(standing, enduring)*". **Able to fig a mirror.** The idiom is still breathing, dying or still alive, being able to endure, being able to stand on one's feet, still having a soul, being able to move.

1. Today I have overworked and I am barely able to fog a mirror.

2. Not everyone is able to fog a mirror after a long conversation with an interviewer.

By origin, all phraseological units are divided into two groups: local and mastered. Below we consider a number of phrases that are widely used in the fiction and their analysis in the English and Uzbek languages.

In English:

A little new to all this (new to all this) is used when a person is new or inexperienced in something, this is all new or new. For example:

1. I am afraid that I am a bit slow. I am **a little new to all this**.

2. Ann is **new to all this**, so she needs practice to get used to it.

Able to breathe easily again (able to breathe freely again) to breathe freely or catch one's breath again after a certain intense process or condition (yengil nafas olmoq).

1. The lesson is over, now you are **able to breathe freely again**.

2. After seeing our guest, we **were able to breathe easily again**.

In Uzbek:

Ko'z ochib yumguncha-In a moment. The given phraseological unit belongs to the literary and colloquial styles. It is used to strengthen the meaning and to draw attention to the speed of the fulfillment of an action. It also has a synonym, "hash-pash deguncha," which is the older one of the phrases.

Example: "*Umr degan narsa ko'z ochib yumguncha otib ketar ekan,*" Mirmuhsin, "Jamila."

Es-hushini yo'qotmoq- to lose one's head, to lose one's mind - tomi ketmoq. The phrase means that many have forgotten them as a result of being severely affected by something.

For instance, *Uning bu ahvolini ko'rib es-hushimni yo'qotib qo'ydim.*

A common feature of idioms in both languages is that they are **idioms in the field of zoonyms**. That is, there are some expressions that contribute to the beauty of our speech that are represented by the names of animals. For example:

In English, a little frog in a big pond is used when one feels uncomfortable or weak in the company of strangers; a little frog in a big lake.

1. When John transferred to another group, he found himself **a little frog in a big pond**.

2. It is a common feeling for newcomers to find themselves **a little frog in a big pond**.

A little bird told me (a little bird whispered me) This expression is used when you have heard or know the word before but do not want to say from whom you heard it.

1. Did you hear that Ann is going to get married? Where did you find this information? **A little bird told me**.

2. **A little bird whispered to me** it was your wedding.

A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush: This idiom means it is better to have something small and certain than the possibility of something greater that may never materialize.

*Prefer the people in front of you, don't dream of everyone. Because **a bird in the hand is worth two in the bush**.*

In Uzbek, "Qush uyasida ko'rganini qiladi" is one of the most used idioms in Uzbek. This idiom is most commonly used in family environment and upbringing, in the sense that the child looks up to the older members of the family.

Qush uyasida ko'rganini qiladi. *Tanqid ostida katta bo'lgan bola boshqalarni yomonlashni o'rganadi. (A child who grows up under criticism learns to criticize others.)*

Idioms are a type of **figurative language** that writers can use to add impact and character to their writing. Through idioms, we can express our unspoken words easily or draw attention by making our speech fluent. For example,

1. Add humor:

Idiomatic expressions can help transform flat descriptions with the help of a funny turn of phrase. For instance, rather than describing someone as not very smart, you could say they are "not the sharpest tool in the shed" or "not the brightest star in the sky."

2. Engage the reader:

By inserting an idiomatic phrase into your writing, you force the reader to shift from thinking literally to thinking abstractly. For example, the idiom “biting off more than they can chew” describes someone taking on a challenging task. Using this idiom can encourage the reader to conjure a visual image in their head.

3. Evoke a specific region:

Certain idioms can be unique to a particular group of people or geographic area. For instance, “that dog won’t hunt” is a common idiom in the Southern United States that means something doesn’t work or make sense.

4. Share a point of view:

Idioms can express commonly shared or universal ideas, so there are often dozens of idioms that apply to the same concept. For example, several idioms express themselves the concept of death. If you were to write that someone “passed away,” you are using an idiom to describe death in a graceful, delicate way. Alternatively, you could say that a person “kicked the bucket,” a much cruder way of describing the act of dying.

Conclusion. Idioms often summarize or reflect a common cultural experience, even if that experience is now outdated or obsolete. Idioms that enrich speech and make it easier to express have their own appearance in every field, in every language. In other words, English and Uzbek idioms are different from Spanish or French idioms. Every language has words or phrases that cannot be understood directly. Even if the meaning of all words is well known and all grammatical expressions are understood, it is still difficult to understand the meaning of an idiomatic expression. Understanding words in proverbs, phrases, and colloquial speech poses a number of difficulties.

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